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IMPORTANCE OF VALUES IN EDUCATION WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO MANAGEMENT

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Abstract

Values are extremely necessary for life, but which are generally ignored by the modern system of education. Today's education lays emphasis on accumulation of factual knowledge, but fails to mould the character of the youth. Our young people therefore have failed to acquire the means by which they can make themselves mentally strong, courageous, bold and upright. Aim of the present study is to find out the values in the youth which will instill a sense of self-confidence and enthusiasm in them. Further the study focuses on the study of the values in Management students. Terminal (End) values and Instrumental (Means) values were measured. The study will bring out the strategies to build effective value system in the management students in order to evolve as an effective managers and individuals.

Key words: *Values, courageous, bold and upright, Terminal (End).*

"The real difficulty is that people have no idea of what education truly is. We assess the value of education in the same manner as we assess the value of land or of shares in the stock-exchange market. We want to provide only such education as would enable the student to earn more. We hardly give any thought to the improvement of the character of the educated. " – Gandhi

"Education process that does not involve itself in proper values or does not lay stress on morals is dangerous. Consequently, the products of the process, who have no sense of values, gradually enter the

positions of higher authority in the administration of nations at very high levels. Hence the world has come to the brink of a disaster. Education can yield peace and prosperity only when along with technical skills and objective information, students are equipped with moral ideals, righteous living and spiritual insight.”

- Bhagawan Sri Saty Saibaba

“Education is the manifestation of perfection already existing in man”. According to him that Education is required by which character is formed, strength of the mind is increased, intellect is expanded and by which one can stand on ones own feet.”

- Swami Vivekananda

“Education to be complete, must be humane. It must include not only the training of the intellect, but the refinement of the heart and the discipline of the spirit”

-Dr. S. Radhakrishnan

INTRODUCTION & REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Value is the manner in which an individual tends to make judgments or choices, both about goals and means, at different stages of one’s life, in different facets of it, as are deemed to lead to the well being and happiness of oneself and the society. Once the value is internalized, it becomes a standard for guiding action or a criterion for selection of an action.

According to Maria Montessori "There is a part of a child's soul that has always been unknown but which must be known. With a spirit of sacrifice and enthusiasm we must go in search like those who travel to foreign lands and tear up mountains in their search for hidden gold. This is what the adults must do who seeks the unknown factor that lies hidden in the depths of a child's soul. This is a labor in which all must share, without distinction of nation, race, or social standing since it means the bringing forth of an indispensable element for the moral progress of mankind."

According to Bhagawan Sri Sathya Sai (1993) The five life-breaths of the students are Truth, Righteousness, Peace, Love and Non-violence. All these five principles have to be rigorously observed to sublimate one's life. Each one should cultivate the qualities of compassion, patience and oneness. These qualities will promote the unity of mankind. These are based on the love-principle. Without love, there is no life. Love gives rise to truth. Love begets peace. When you have love, you practice non-violence. Love is the under-current in all these.

According to Harshsalunke (2011) The more practical aspects of 'education' involved alongside intellectual training, the laying of a moral foundation which helped to make the individual a good citizen who was conscious of his innate strength.

According to Singh, MR et.al (2006) as explained in their article “Evolving role of value-based higher education in India”, revealed that teaching methods faculty primarily selects to use reflect who they are and what they believe. In particular, those who are more highly Spiritual based on their own self-identification, the personal priority they place on seeking opportunities to grow Spiritually and the Personal Value they attribute to integrating Spirituality in their lives are much more likely to use Student-Centered Pedagogical methods when teaching students.

They opined that Faculty attitudes and behaviors are known to have important implications for student development. The actions of faculty, both within and outside the classroom, impact the learning and development of future teachers, lawyers, physicians and policymakers, not to mention their very own academic successors and the thousands of others whose work affects our daily lives.

Importance of Values in the Society

We have values for ourselves and values for society. These values may be the same or they may differ. For example, you may believe that you should be forgiving of others, but that society should be less concerned with being forgiving.

According to Debbarma (2014) If any ethics are primarily to help a person to live a just and righteous life with him/her and in relation to others, ethics too is similarly oriented towards a righteous life. The personal and social life of every individual is permeated by a great sense of righteousness.

Without this possibility of constituting the world-view of the community and the possibility of the individuals striving to achieve it, a value system can only be either an item in the "thought-museum" of cultural artifacts or a fantasy. It is perpetual preparedness to make cultural changes with a view to obtaining this balance (Anthony Giddens, 2011).

According to Yogi (2009) Education is not only for news but also for views; it is not only for information but also for inspiration; it is not only educating but also enlightening. It is quite an integrated process. An educated person should have all kind of qualities. Education should make every individual capable physically, mentally, intellectually, emotionally and spiritually. Therefore, some universal ideals of "love, peace, respect, tolerance, forgiveness, co-existence and non-violence" should be accepted by all the educators worldwide. These values are truly

indispensable, devoid of which, our society cannot sustain itself and people will forget humanity. And, we can easily imagine the future ahead and foresee what our future will be like. No matter what our religious beliefs are, what our practices are, but there are ultimate goals which one has to achieve in life. Everyone always aspires to love, peace and happiness, and that includes a spiritually balanced life. Even a person who may not be spiritual should also believe and practice the ideals of love, peace, tolerance and service.

Rokeach (1973) defined values as 'enduring beliefs that a specific mode of conduct or end-state of existence is personally or socially preferable to an opposite or converse mode of conduct or end-state of existence. 'According to him, Terminal Values refer to desirable end states of existence; the goals that a person would like to achieve during their lifetime and may vary among different groups of people in different cultures. Instrumental Values refer to preferable modes of behavior. These are preferable modes of behavior, or means of achieving the terminal values.

According to Vikram Karve (2011) there are two types of values namely

1. INSTRUMENTAL VALUES: These are core values, permanent in nature, comprise personal characteristics and character traits. Instrumental Values refer to preferable modes of behaviour and include values like honesty, sincerity, ambition, independence, obedience, imaginativeness, courageousness, competitiveness, and also some negative traits too.

2. TERMINAL VALUES: Terminal Values are those things that we can work towards or we think are most important and we feel are most desirable – terminal values are desirable states of existence. Terminal Values include things like happiness, self respect, family security, recognition, freedom, inner harmony, comfortable life, professional excellence, etc

In a nutshell, **Terminal Values** signify the **objectives** of the life of a person – the ultimate things the person wants to achieve through his or her behaviour (the destination he wants to reach in life) whereas **Instrumental Values** indicate the **methods** an individual would like to adopt for achieving his life’s aim (the path he would like to take to reach his destination)

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To study the significance of Terminal and Instrumental values
2. To study the gender difference in the choice of values
3. To suggest the ways to inculcate values in students
4. To suggest measures for the educational institutions to embed the values in the students

METHODOLOGY

Sample size is 150 management graduates. 60 girls and 90 boys. Respondents were taken from three Management Institutes in Bangalore. Primary data was collected using questionnaire. Questionnaires consisted of list of Terminal and Instrumental values.

The table 1 below shows the Terminal and Instrumental values which are used in the present study

Terminal (End) Values	Instrumental (Means) Values
Achievement	Action-oriented
Aesthetics	Ambitious
Contentment	Athletic/Physical
Equality	Brave
Excitement	Compassionate
Harmony	Competent
Health	Considerate
Liberty	Creative
Love	Decisive
Peace	Dependable
Pleasure	Disciplined
Prosperity	Energetic
Security	Friendly
Self-esteem	Good-natured
Social status	Honest
Spirituality	Intelligent
Wisdom	Open
	Orderly
	Outgoing
	Rational
	Reserved
	Spontaneous
	Tough-minded

Respondents have to rank the terminal (I to 17) and instrumental values (1 to 23) based on their priority. Data collected was further analyzed to derive necessary conclusions and develop possible strategies to inculcate values in the students.

RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

Table 2 shows the Average ranking of choice of values of respondents (Girls & Boys)

Terminal Values (End)	Average Ranking		Instrumental Values (Means)	Average Ranking	
	Girls	Boys		Girls	Boys
Achievement	2	1	Action-oriented	4	5
Aesthetics	11	14	Ambitious	1	4
Contentment	10	12	Athletic/Physical	5	6
Equality	12	13	Brave	6	13
Excitement	9	5	Compassionate	11	18
Harmony	13	10	Competent	2	17
Health	1	6	Considerate	16	16
Liberty	16	15	Creative	20	20
Love	3	7	Decisive	19	19
Peace	15	11	Dependable	15	15
Pleasure	4	2	Disciplined	7	14
Prosperity	8	8	Energetic	3	7
Security	5	9	Friendly	8	1
Self-esteem	7	3	Good-natured	9	8
Social status	6	4	Honest	23	2
Spirituality	17	17	Intelligent	10	10
Wisdom	14	16	Open	14	11
			Orderly	17	9
			Outgoing	13	3
			Rational	18	12
			Reserved	21	23
			Spontaneous	12	22
			Tough-minded	22	21

The above table the top five Terminal values for girls are Health, Achievement, Love, Pleasure and Security in the same order of ranking. Boys top five Terminal values are Achievement, Pleasure, Self-esteem, Social Status and Excitement. Pertaining to Instrumental values, girls top five values are Ambitious, Competent, Energetic, Honest and Athletic/Physical. Boys top five Instrumental values are Friendly, Honest, Outgoing, Ambitious and Action-oriented. The results reveals that girls have ranked *Health* first in the Terminal value and *Ambitious* as Instrumental value. Boys opted *Achievement* first in Terminal values and *Friendly* among Instrumental values. Harmony, Wisdom, Peace, Liberty and Spirituality were the last five Terminal values among girls. Equality, Aesthetics, Liberty, Wisdom and Spirituality were the last five Terminal values among boys. Decisive, Creative, Reserved, Tough-minded and Honesty were the less prioritized Instrumental values by girls. Decisive, Creative, Tough-minded, Spontaneous and Reserved were the less prioritized Instrumental values by boys.

Results reveal that the most important Terminal values in the present society like Peace, Spirituality, Equality, Harmony and Aesthetics are less priority for the management graduates. Being Spontaneous, Decisive, Honesty and Creative are the least prioritized Instrumental values of the management graduates which will build the value system of the society.

Table 3 Shows the Top Five Terminal and Instrumental ranking of

Rank	Terminal Value	Instrumental Value
1	Health	Ambitious
2	Achievement	Competent
3	Love	Energetic
4	Pleasure	Honest
5	Security	Athletic/Physical

Table 4 Shows the Top Five Terminal and Instrumental ranking of Boys

Rank	Terminal Value	Instrumental Value
1	Achievement	Friendly
2	Pleasure	Honest
3	Self-esteem	Outgoing
4	Social Status	Ambitious
5	Excitement	Action-oriented

Table 5 Shows the Bottom Five Terminal and Instrumental ranking of

Rank	Terminal Value	Instrumental Value
13	Harmony	Equality
14	Wisdom	Aesthetics
15	Peace	Liberty
16	Liberty	Wisdom
17	Spirituality	Spirituality

Table 6 Shows the Bottom Five Terminal and Instrumental ranking of Boys

Rank	Terminal Value	Instrumental Value
19	Decisive	Decisive
20	Creative	Creative
21	Reserved	Tough-minded
22	Tough-minded	Spontaneous
23	Honest	Reserved

The values ranked by the students gives us an insight into what is that management students value more and by using what values that they want to reach there. Important Terminal values like Peace, Spirituality, Harmony, Equality and for present generation of management graduates and the Instrumental values Honest, Creative, Decisive, Tough-minded, Aesthetics are less important for the students. To inculcate the above values in the students change has to happen at every level be it the

Universities, Institutes and teachers. The values which will help in the positive development of the individual student as well as society has to inculcated through education. Education with value inculcation should be the focus of the Education System. Different people play significant role in the value inculcation like the Parents, Peers, Siblings and more importantly the Teachers. Present study focuses on the role of the Teachers and Educational Institutes and suggestions are given and ways are proposed to inculcate values in the students.

SUGGESTED WAYS TO INCULCATE VALUES IN THE STUDENTS

1. Vision and mission of the Institute should state the values and importance of their inculcation in the students – Through the Vision the Mission of the Institute, the emphasis of the values has to be continuously imbibed in the mind of the students through displaying of it in the key places which reminds them of their duties and responsibilities.

2. Revamping the teaching-learning process by framing life-oriented syllabus not exam-oriented – The entire teaching-learning process has to be restructured in order to bring in the component of value education. The syllabus should not just focus on how to score well in the exams but should help the student to understand how to live? And how to make this world a better place to live in.

3. By hiring trained, committed and spiritually-oriented teachers – Institutes has to hire dedicated, committed and spiritually-oriented teachers who can do justice in value inculcation in the students.

4. The teacher should be a role model in demonstrating the values which he/she wants to inculcate. Teacher should have unselfish care and concern for the students.

5. The pedagogical methods for implementing Values like, Autobiographies of leaders, moral stories , Success stories of following values in business, role-plays has to be a part of their routine in the college.

6. By incorporating more activities, games and role-plays involving teams which enhances communication and interpersonal relationships and develops caring, loving and belongingness.

7. Celebrating all festivals and inspiring the students to accept the fellow-beings and people around them. Inculcating importance festival in the text books and making it a part of their education and making them appreciate the culture.

8. Teaching scriptures like Ramayana, Mahabharata and Bhagavatam and the importance of values and their application can bring significant change in the mindset of the students.

9. Creating stress, anxiety and fear free environment by making students allot daily some time in practicing Pranayama and meditation.

10. The whole environment of the Institute should reflect the feeling of togetherness and oneness.

11. Involving students more in community service and charity and socially responsible activities will enhance the service – orientedness.

12. A constant and unvarying repetition of the same message or of the same expectations has a conditioning effect.

CONCLUSION

Education should foster morality, righteousness and character. Man today has acquired prodigious knowledge in the fields of science and technology. But this serves only to promote a material civilisation and teaches only knowledge of the external worlds to students. What man truly needs today is not this external knowledge. He needs refinement of the heart. This can be got only by internal culture.

It is not enough today to make a man a mere human being. He has to be transformed into an ideal human being. Education makes a man compassionate. That is the fulfillment of the purpose of education. Education should not be equated with book knowledge or the acquisition of skills for leading one's life in the world. The modern student is unable to determine what is the basis of his life and what is important in it. Hence, he loses confidence in himself.

An attempt has been made in the present study to understand the priorities of the Terminal Values and Instrumental Values among the management graduates. Effort has to be made by the Universities and colleges to inculcate the value based education in the curriculum and recruit dedicated teachers who will act as role models for the students and stand as live examples in implementing what they teach. Suggestions to the educational system focuses on the ways to implement the same in the schools and colleges has been made which will really help us, the teachers to imbibe values in our students, who are the citizens of the nation.

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